

IMPACT OF UNEMPLOYMENT TO WELL BEING AND LIFE SATISFACTION

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Abstract: This study examined the impact of unemployment on respondents' wellbeing and life satisfaction. A quantitative method and comparative descriptive design were used in the study. This method and design are suitable for the study's objective to determine the differences in the respondent's level of wellbeing and life satisfaction according to their sex, age, marital status, educational attainment, and number of dependents. The statistical tests utilized in the study were the percentage, mode, Mann-Whitney U, and Kruskal Wallis. The data for this study was gathered from different barangays of Mandaluyong City, including, but not limited to, Brgy. Addition Hills, Brgy, Barangka, and Brgy. Hulo. The study's results revealed that a significant number of respondents were female. Most respondents, ages 40-50, were high school graduates as their highest educational attainment. Almost half of the unemployed were married with two (2) to four (4) dependents. The respondents' life satisfaction level indicated they were either moderately or delighted with their lives. In addition, most respondents indicated they were slightly satisfied with their lives. Per their level of well-being the majority of the respondents indicated that their level of well-being was moderate. It explains that there is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction regarding sex, age, marital status, and number of dependents. On the other hand, educational attainment indicates a significant difference to consider when analyzing life satisfaction levels in the examined 151,473 people. However, there is no significant difference in level of well-being in terms of sex, age, educational background, marital status, and number of dependents. With these findings, the researchers recommended giving unemployed people access to mental health resources such as counseling or therapy can be beneficial. Also, the national governments should prioritize education and training programs that equip individuals with the skills and knowledge needed to succeed in the modern job market. Moreover, local governments should work to increase funding for mental health facilities and services that cater specifically to the needs of the unemployed. It can include support groups, therapy sessions, and counseling services specifically designed to address the difficulties unemployed face. Lastly, please encourage students to finish college to help them avoid unemployment. Studies show that those with college degrees are less likely to be jobless than people without degrees because those who have completed college have the information and abilities necessary to succeed in the work market of today, making them more appealing prospects for employers.

Keywords: Unemployment, Life Satisfaction, Mental Health, Well being.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment is one of the severe and persistent issues faced by economies worldwide. Over the last few decades, economists, psychologists, and sociologists have published numerous studies examining the influence of unemployment on subjective individual well-being. Based on the Bureau of Labor Statistics, the term "unemployed" refers to individuals who do not currently hold a paid employment position, have made job-related inquiries within the most recent four weeks, and are available for work. In addition, employees who were temporarily removed from their positions but were later reinstated will also be counted since they anticipate being summoned back to work (Bureau of Labor Statistics, 2015).

The health of unemployed employees is lower than that of their employed counterparts. In the study of Farré et al. (2018), they have less confidence in themselves, appear overwhelmed by their difficulties, and report significantly more mental disorders. It is safe to assume that well-being has a strong relationship with unemployment. In addition to developing, one's

potential, having a sense of purpose, exercising control over one's life, and having positive connections, well-being is the encounter of positive emotions such as satisfaction and happiness. A sustained situation enables an individual or population to survive and flourish.

Diverse economists emphasize the importance of well-being insights and policy implications. They argue that well-being is both a societal and an individual goal. Additionally, happier citizens benefit society. Even though the actual causal factor remains elusive and despite the contradictory findings of several studies, it appears that happier people are productive. In addition to being more social and healthier, they are more cooperative at work. When a culture reaches a certain level of economic development, not only are its economic outcomes and indicators indicative of that stage of economic development capable of predicting what its inhabitant's value, but that culture is also capable of predicting what its inhabitants value. Consequently, unemployment and well-being impact people's life satisfaction (Ruggeri et al., 2020).

Life satisfaction is a person's overall assessment of their life and how well they feel their expectations and aspirations have been met. It is a personal evaluation of one's opinion of one's life's circumstances, considering elements like fulfillment, happiness, and feeling of purpose. Many variables, such as personal values, social connections, economic standing, and health, impact life pleasure. It is a crucial indicator of someone's well-being and quality of life, and it is frequently used to assess how well social policies and interventions that try to improve people's lives are working. There is a constant inverse relationship between life happiness and unemployment. Compared to employed people, unemployed people frequently report lower levels of life satisfaction. It can be related to several things, including the loss of social standing, self-esteem, and income that comes with losing a job. Also, the strain and anxiety that come with being jobless can amplify unpleasant feelings and lower general life satisfaction. Furthermore, a person's general well-being can be significantly impacted by unemployment.

Unemployment's associated lack of financial security can exacerbate stress, worry, and despair. Also, it may lead to reduced healthcare access and a rise in the risk of physical and mental health issues. In addition to social isolation and fewer opportunities for personal development, unemployment can also hurt a person's well-being. Most current studies consider an individual's well-being to determine unemployment's positive and negative effects on well-being. To provide a more nuanced investigation of how unemployment impacts overall wellbeing, we researchers incorporated life satisfaction. Most research conducted nowadays concentrates on adult populations, leaving out younger adults and older people (such as those with conditions that prevent them from working, for example). It would be possible to create customized interventions and tactics among these distinct demographics if more research were conducted on the impact of unemployment on well-being and life satisfaction

A. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to the Social Comparison Theory by Leon Festinger (1954), people assess their own social and individual worth by comparing themselves to others. We all contrast our looks with those of media-presented celebrities, our skills with those of our coworkers, and many facets of our social lives. Social comparison theory may be able to explain how unemployed people compare themselves to others and how this comparison may affect their well-being in the context of unemployment.

More specifically, the social comparison theory contends that people regularly make upward and downward comparisons. Self-comparison to those who are seen to be wealthier or more successful is referred to as an upward comparison while doing the opposite with those who are thought to be less wealthy or successful is referred to as a downward comparison. While comparing themselves to others who are employed and feeling less successful, unemployed people may participate in upward comparisons in the context of unemployment. Feelings of inadequacy, low self-esteem, and decreased well-being might result. Those unemployed may also encounter social stigma or sense judgment from others, worsening these unfavorable emotions. Those who are unemployed, however, may also make unfavorable comparisons by contrasting themselves with other unemployed people or people who have gone through comparable job losses. It can foster a sense of community and social support, which can lessen the detrimental effects of unemployment on well-being.

The social comparison thought generally asserts that comparisons with others substantially influence how people perceive their abilities and well-being. These comparisons in the context of unemployment may affect how people perceive their situation and how they handle its stress and uncertainty. Interventions intended to lessen the detrimental effects of unemployment can be informed by understanding these social comparisons and their impact on wellbeing.

In summary, it can help explain how unemployment can lead to adverse wellbeing and life satisfaction outcomes. Understanding the impact of resource deprivation on unemployed individuals is essential for developing effective policies and interventions that can help mitigate the adverse effects of unemployment and support those who are experiencing it.

B. CONCEPTUAL MODEL

FIGURE I: RESEARCH PARADIGM

The researchers used this model as the paradigm of this proposed study. It shows the impact of unemployment on two variables: life satisfaction and wellbeing of the respondents. Through this paradigm, the researchers were able to determine differences in the level of life satisfaction and level of well-being when the responders were categorized by their profile.

C. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This proposed research study aims to determine the impact of unemployment on the well-being and life satisfaction of the selected unemployed respondent's residents in Mandaluyong City. Specifically, this study aimed to respond to the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Age
 - 1.3. Marital Status
 - 1.4. Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.5. Number of dependent(s)
2. What is the assessed level of life satisfaction of the respondents?
3. What is the assessed level of well-being of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant difference among the level of life satisfaction of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile?
5. Is there a significant difference among the level of well-being of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile?

D. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level.

H₀₁ There is no significant difference among the life satisfaction level of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference among the level of well-being of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile.

E. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Stated below are the individuals, groups of people, or institution/s that would benefit from the results of this study, as follows:

Unemployed individuals. This study will help them analyze the negative effects of unemployment and its effect on well-being and life satisfaction. Moreover, this study gives them an idea that they need to upgrade their status to fulfill their wellbeing and life satisfaction.

Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE). This study will help the department know that many are still unemployed for various reasons such as low completed education. Moreover, they may help or provide job seekers with opportunities to work.

Local Government of Mandaluyong. The results of this study will help make the Mandaluyong government aware that there are many unemployed in their area and help to reduce it. It will help them pay attention to the unemployed and build a program where there is a place for everyone. Those who need work will come to job fairs organized by the local government, the same with other cities here in NCR.

Students. This study will help them appreciate their education and have more career opportunities because one of the essential requirements when looking for a job is a high level of education. It will help them have an idea about being unemployed and let it be an inspiration not to give up and continue in life to get a better future and to fulfill their life satisfaction.

Workers. This study will serve as an eye-opener for the workers to value the work they currently are employed at and improve their skills for future promotion. Future Researchers. The study will be helpful for academics who intend to conduct studies explicitly analyzing the relationship among unemployment, wellbeing and quality of life.

F. SCOPE AND DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study aimed to determine and assess the well-being and life satisfaction of the selected unemployed respondents residing in Mandaluyong City. This research was conducted at the three (3) Barangays in Mandaluyong City, namely Barangay Hulo, including three hundred-five (305) unemployed residents.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority 2021 preliminary yearly labor market figures, the National Capital Region's unemployment rate was 10.6% based on Mandaluyong Gov Ph. In the City of Mandaluyong, the labor force is 58.40%, with 86.4% of workers employed and 13.60% without jobs. The highest population in Mandaluyong City and the researchers decided to include the barangay of Mandaluyong City, which is Barangay Barangka Itaas, Addition Hills, and Barangay Hulo since these three barangays have a high population and unemployment rate.

This research study occurs in the academic year 2022- 2023. The researchers used standardized questionnaires to gather the necessary data and information from the individuals.

Direct supervision and monitoring of how a participant responds to the questionnaire are observed to reduce risk, as well as a thorough explanation of a specific item if the question is not understood. Other external factors that may influence the proposed investigation and its potential outcomes but are not addressed or covered under the scope are all circumscribed.

G. DEFINITIONS OF TERMS

The words that were technically and operationally used as follows: Anxiety. According to the American Psychological Association (2022),

Anxiety is characterized by tense feelings, worry-inducing thoughts, and physical changes, including increased blood pressure. People with anxiety disorders frequently experience intrusive thoughts or anxieties repeatedly. Out of dread, they might avoid certain situations. Physical side effects such as shaking, sweating, nausea, and increased heartbeat are also possible.

Depression. In accordance with the World Health Organization, depression is a common form of mental disorder. Its distinguishing characteristics include persistent sadness and a lack of interest in formerly gratifying or enjoyable activities. It may also affect sleep and appetite. Problems with concentration and exhaustion are common.

Employee is a person who works for an employer to complete a specific assignment. Employee compensation, scheduling, and working conditions are all at the employer's discretion. Contractors do not receive incentives, whereas employees do (Heathfield, S. 2022).

Jobless people are deemed to be unemployed if they are actively looking for work and are thought to be employable. This group includes those who are in the workforce but do not have acceptable occupations (Loo, A. 2023).

Mental Health. WHO defines mental well-being as "a state of well-being in which the individual realizes his or her abilities, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and can contribute to his or her community" (Galderisi, Silvana, et al. 2015).

Minimum Wage is the least amount of money an employer is required to pay wage earners for work done during a specific period, which a collective bargaining agreement or a personal contract cannot decrease (International Labour Organisation. 2015).

Non-workers are only permitted entry inside the facility if a staff member escorts them. For people who are not employed, there are income support programs (Cambridge, 2023).

Salary includes all payments provided to employees for physical or mental labor, but they do not include the earnings of independent contractors (Schmitt, H.2018).

Satisfaction is a function of stable traits. In other words, certain people are more content with their lives depending on who they are, according to their satisfaction with several aspects of life. Work, family, health, and leisure are just a few of life's many different but interconnected fields (Bauer et al.,2012)

Self-esteem is an oversimplified word for complicated mental states related to one's perception of oneself. Self-esteem makes it possible to identify low self-esteem's origins, predict the impacts of those reasons, and plan the troubleshooting process for finding the philosophical faults or psychological scars that produce it (Bailey, J. 2003).

Unemployed. According to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (2017) unemployed workers, their families, and the country suffer. Employees and their families suffer financial losses, and the country loses out on the potential production of goods and services. Additionally, the decreased spending power of these individuals could result in the loss of more jobs.

Unemployment is defined as a situation in which individuals actively seeking work cannot find employment. It is measured by the percentage of the unemployed workforce or the unemployment rate. A more thorough definition is provided by the International Labor Organization (ILO), which states that "unemployment occurs when people are without work and actively seeking work within the last four weeks but are unable to find it" (ILO, 2006).

Well-Being. The modern definition of well-being goes beyond being filled with good feelings to prospering in various spheres of life. Hedonistic and eudaemonic aspects of well-being are combined to create well-being (Adler, A., & Seligman, M. E.,2016).

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. RESEARCH METHOD

This study utilizes a quantitative approach to determine the assessed wellbeing and life satisfaction of the selected unemployed respondents residing in Mandaluyong City. The approach was chosen to fulfill and accomplish the study's goals: investigate phenomena and their interactions using data and variables that were systematically measured. The researchers used quantitative research to describe the respondents based on their profile background and correlate their life satisfaction and well-being to the profile background. The quantitative approach is used in the research process to prove, refute, or support pre-existing theories. This type of research measures variables and looks at relationships between variables to find patterns, correlations, or causal connections.

Quantitative research is based on data collected by researchers from various fields, which is observed and measured as well as research. Forming hypotheses or theories is typically the first step in quantitative research. It is based on data collected by researchers from various fields, which is observed, measured, and researched. Forming hypotheses or theories is typically the first step in quantitative analysis; inferential statistics are usually used. After the study, the researchers can determine whether the hypotheses presented should be rejected or accepted. Neutrality, objectivity, and the values that underpin quantitative research and statistical analysis of a significant sample are the gathering of a wide range of knowledge and these two things. (Leavy P, 2020).

According to Ariola (2006), Descriptive research explains how closely two or more variables are related. The researcher studied the association, considering the differences between the two variables. This study strategy is straightforward, making it easier for the researcher to gather information and data. The comparative descriptive design is used to explain variables and look at differences in variables that naturally arise in two or more groups in a situation. Comparative descriptive designs compare descriptive information from distinct groups. As a result, the researchers were able to determine how factors such as sex, age, marital status, level of education, and the number of dependents relate to the happiness and well-being of Filipinos.

B. POPULATION FRAME AND SAMPLING

The study's target population was gathered from Mandaluyong, specifically in three (3) Barangays, namely Brgy. Addition Hills, Brgy. Barangka Itaas, and Brgy. Hulo. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), the barangay's population is 108,896, 11,242, and 31,335, respectively. Using the G*Power version 3.1.9.4 with effect size $f = 0.25$, an alpha level of 0.05, a power of 0.95, and five (5) groups, the computed sample size is equivalent to 305 (with the actual power of 95.21%)

This research utilized a purposive type of sampling. Purposive sampling is a type in which individuals are chosen as samples as their controls for the researcher's purposes (Garcia et al., 2011). The researchers used this method to select respondents based on the purpose of this study. This technique is also known as judgmental sampling.

This sampling design is about selecting individuals as part of the sample; however, not all are allowed to be included in the sample because the criteria are based on the investigator's purpose. Thus, these unemployed residents of the said barangays were chosen as respondents under the guidance of the researchers to avoid disturbance and to have simple access to the participants.

It was also highlighted how important it was for participants to be available, willing, and able to share their experiences understandably. As a result, a total of three barangay captains and representatives were interviewed.

C. DESCRIPTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

The respondents in the study included 305 unemployed residents from three barangays, namely Brgy. Addition Hills, Brgy. Barangka Itaas, and Brgy. Hulo Mandaluyong City. These residents were identified depending on their sex, age, marital status, highest level of education, and number of dependents. There are 157 unemployed females and 148 unemployed males. Conversely, sixty-three residents are on the range of 18-28; Sixty-five residents are 29-39 years old; Sixty-eight residents are 40-50 years old; Fifty-four residents are 51-59 years old; and fifty-five residents are 60 years old and above. Furthermore, 114 were unemployed singles, 144 were unemployed married, 12 were separated, 27 were unemployed widowed, and eight were divorced. Moreover, 62 residents have completed primary or no education, 20 have completed vocational courses, 159 were high school graduates, 32 had two years of college, and 32 had completed their 4 years course.

Also, 137 unemployed residents had 2-4 dependents, 103 residents had 0-1 dependents, 51 unemployed had 5-6 dependents, 12 of them had 7-8, and 2 of them had 9 and above dependents.

D. INSTRUMENT USED

Two measures in the form of standardized survey questionnaires were evaluated in order to determine how unemployment affected life satisfaction and well-being. The researcher sought validation by writing to a specialist who examined and validated the three sets of questionnaires. The researchers used a standardized questionnaire to get the overall and detailed statistics depending on the research subject. It was utilized to gather pertinent information for the analysis. To conduct the survey, the researcher provided the participants with a questionnaire.

1. Life Satisfaction Scale

To gauge the respondents' level of life satisfaction, the researchers employed a questionnaire and scale from the Satisfaction with Life Scale by (Diener et al., 1985). The SWLS is a quick 5-item survey to gauge general cognitive evaluations of life satisfaction. The average time it takes for respondents to complete a Likert scale response is one minute. The open-ended nature of the questions makes this scale suitable for adults from various backgrounds. A group of experts reviewed the questionnaire and gave their approval. We looked at the structure of the instrument to determine whether each statement measured the intended construct.

Scale	Scoring	Interpretation
7	31-35	Extremely Satisfied
6	26-30	Satisfied
5	21-25	Slightly Satisfied
4	20	Neutral
3	15-19	Slightly Dissatisfied
2	10-14	Dissatisfied
1	5-9	Extremely Dissatisfied

By pre-testing the questionnaire on 30 respondents who matched the actual resident respondents' characteristics, the questionnaire's reliability was ascertained. Checking revealed that the Cronbach Alpha was 0.887, which is satisfactory.

2. Psychological Well-Being Scale

To gauge the respondents' well-being, the researchers employed a questionnaire and the Psychological Well-Being Scale (Ryff & Keyes, 1995). Psychological Well-being Scale (PWB) is a tool or questionnaire that consists of 18 questions and is used to assess a person's level of well-being about several psychological characteristics. The scale typically consists of several questions or statements that rate many facets of psychological health, including autonomy, self-acceptance, positive relationships, personal development, and purpose in life.

The satisfaction with the questionnaire was validated like that of the life satisfaction scale. Experts evaluated the questions in the instrument to see if they measured the things they claimed to measure

Scale	Interpretation
1	Strongly Agree
2	Somewhat Agree
3	Little Agree
4	Neither Agree or Disagree
5	Little Disagree
6	Somewhat Disagree
7	Strongly Disagree
Scoring	Interpretation
95 - 126	High
64 - 94	Above Average
32 - 63	Moderate
18 - 31	Low

The final form of the instrument has considered and incorporated the opinions and recommendations of the experts. By choosing 30 people to participate in the survey and submit their answers, the validity and precision of the survey instrument were evaluated. Based on the outcome, it had an excellent Cronbach alpha of 0.78.

E. DATA GATHERING PROCEDURE

After approving our letter to survey Rizal Technological University, the researchers had a set of questionnaires to collect the information needed to conduct the research, 305 unemployed participants are needed.

A combination of relevant questions taken from prior studies and original questions developed by the researchers were used to create the survey. Copies of the questionnaire were given to the unemployed respondents residing in Mandaluyong City after the professor approved it. Before asking each resident if they would be willing and interested in participating in the study, the researchers discussed its significance and connection to the current issues.

The researcher collected, analyzed, and tallied the data of results for interpretation on how unemployment affects the respondent's well-being and life satisfaction after the respondents completed the questionnaire.

F. STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

The statistical treatments below were utilized to appropriately analyzed and interpreted the data gathered in the survey:

1. Percentage

The percentage is one of the most usual methods to portray statistics and the symbol to apply it is “%” (Statistics Canada, 2015). This statistical test was utilized to show the percentage of the unemployed according to their demographic profile.

Formula:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 10$$

Where:

P = Percentage

f = frequency of each group of students in the sample size

n = sample size

2. Mode

A data set's mode is its value with the highest frequency of occurrence. A data set could have one mode, several modes, or none (Hayes, 2022). It is used to present and measure the most responses of the unemployed respondents in life satisfaction and well-being.

$$Mo = l + \left(\frac{f_1 - f_0}{2f_1 - f_0 - f_2} \right) h$$

Where:

l = lower limit of the modal class

h = size of the class interval (assuming all class sizes are equal)

f1 = frequency of modal class

f0 = frequency of the class preceding the modal class

f2 = frequency of the class succeeding the modal class

3. Mann-Whitney U test

It is a non-parametric test that assesses whether or not two sample means from the same population are equal by comparing their respective means. The Mann-Whitney U test is typically employed when the data is ordinal, or the t-test's assumptions are broken (Statistics Solutions, 2021). This test was utilized to find the difference in level of life satisfaction and level of well-being in terms of sex.

Formula:

$$U = N_1 + N_2 - \frac{n_1(n_1 + 1)}{2} - \sum_{i=n_1+1}^{n_2} R_i$$

U = Mann-Whitney U test

n1 = Sample size of first sample

n2 = Sample size of second sample

Ri = Standard deviation of first sample

4. Kruskal-Wallis Test

It is to ascertain whether there is a difference in life satisfaction and wellbeing regarding marital status, highest educational attainment, and number of dependents. The purpose of this test, which is the non-parametric counterpart of one-way analysis

of variance, is to ascertain if there is a distinction between two or more independent variable groupings on an ordinal or continuous dependent variable that did not adhere to one-way ANOVA's assumptions, particularly the assumption of normality of the data distribution. The data in the examples above are not normally distributed, according to the normality test results (Laerd Statistics, 2014).

Formula:

$$H = \left[\frac{12}{n(n+1)} \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{T_j^2}{n_j} \right] - 3(n+1)$$

H = Kruskal Wallis Test

n= is the sum of sample sizes for all samples

tj = is the sum of ranks in the jth sample

c = is the number of samples

nj = is the size of the jth sample

III. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

A. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

DISTRIBUTION OF THE UNEMPLOYED BY SEX

Table 1 Profile Background of the Unemployed in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Female	157	51.5
Male	148	48.5
Total	305	100.0

Table 1 summarizes the sex profile of the unemployed. With 305 responses, most of the unemployed, accounting for 157 responses (51.5% of the response rate), belong to the sex group of females. In contrast, 148, or 48.5% of the total population, belong to the male sex group. In 2020, 326,000 women lost their jobs compared to 141,000 men. Before the crisis, women's labor force participation in the European nation was significantly lower than that of men (56.2% vs. 74.6%), and it decreased even more during it (3.7% for women and 1.2% for men). However, specific challenges and disparities may exist for unemployed individuals based on gender. Women, for example, may face hiring discrimination or be paid less than men with comparable qualifications. They may also be disproportionately impacted by job loss because of caregiving responsibilities or systemic biases in specific industries. The fact that more women than men are leaving the workforce in these, and other economies raises serious concerns for women's empowerment. (International Labour Organization, 2017).

DISTRIBUTION OF THE UNEMPLOYED BY AGE

Table 2 Profile Background of the Unemployed in terms of Age

Age	Count	Percentage
18-28	63	20.7%
29-39	65	21.3%
40-50	68	22.3%
51-59	54	17.7%
60 and above	55	18%
Total	305	100%

Table 2 shows the age profile of the unemployed shows that most respondents are between 40 and 50, accounting for 68 responses or 22.3% of the total. The age group of 29 to 39 comes in second, with 65 responses, or 21.3% of the total. With 63 responders or 20.7% of the total, 18–28 is the third most prevalent group. 60 and older respondents make up the fourth most numerous categories, accounting for 55 respondents overall and 18% of the total. Finally, the age range of 51 to 59 has the fewest participation (54), making up 17.7% of the total. These findings demonstrate the broad age range of the unemployed population, with substantial representation in all age groups, from younger people in their late teens to older people in their 60s and beyond. However, A 40–50-year-old unemployed person is in the middle of their career and may have years of experience in their field. Furthermore, this age group may face age discrimination in the job market, with employers preferring to hire younger workers for entry-level positions or positions requiring less experience (Axelrad et al., 2018).

DISTRIBUTION OF THE UNEMPLOYED BY EDUCATIONAL ATTAINMENT

Table 3 Demographic Profile of the Unemployed in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Count	Percentage
Elementary	62	20.3%
High School	159	52.1%
Vocational	20	6.6%
2 years college	32	10.5%
4 years college	32	10.5%
Total	305	100%

Table 3 presents that the educational attainment profile of the unemployed shows 159 responses, or 52.1% of the total, or respondents having only completed high school. Respondents with elementary education come in second, accounting for 62 responses, or 20.3% of the total. Thirty-two responses each, or 10.5% of the total, were submitted by respondents with less than two years of college education and those with more than four years. Lastly, with 20 responses, or 6.6% of the total, vocational education is the next most popular type of schooling. According to these results, most of the unemployed have a high school diploma, with smaller percentages having earned an elementary, vocational, or college degree. As a result, unemployment among high school graduates can be attributed to various factors, including a lack of required skills and qualifications, competition from college graduates and more experienced workers, and a difficult job market. Many employers in today's job market require a post-secondary education or specialized training for entry-level positions, putting high school graduates at a disadvantage.

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted the labor market, resulting in widespread layoffs and hiring freezes. Several strategies can be pursued to address the high unemployment among high school graduates. One is to encourage more young people to pursue post-secondary education or vocational training programs that will provide them with the skills and qualifications required to succeed in today's competitive environment (National Center for Education Statistics, 2017).

DISTRIBUTION OF THE UNEMPLOYED BY MARITAL STATUS

Table 4 Distribution of the Unemployed by Marital Status

Marital Status	Count	Percent
Single	114	37.4%
Married	144	47.2%
Separated	12	3.9%
Divorced	8	2.6%
Widowed	27	8.9%
Total	305	100%

Table 4 summarizes the marital status profile of the unemployed and shows that most respondents are married or single. Notably, 144 respondents, or 47.2% of the total, report being married, compared to 114 or 37.4% who report being single. With 12 responders or 3.9% of the total, separated people represent a smaller percentage of the population. With 8 respondents or 2.6% of the total, divorced people comprise an even smaller group than overall respondents. Finally, 27 responders, or 8.9% of the total, are widowed. According to these results, most respondents who are unemployed are either married or single, while lesser percentages report being separated, divorced, or widowed.

Brand (2015) states that unemployment among married people can occur for various reasons. First, Job loss due to layoffs or company closures can affect married people in a relationship. If one partner loses their job, the family may face financial difficulties and struggle to meet their basic needs. It may also impact the other partner's employment situation, as they may need to take on more work or change their work schedule to accommodate changes in their family's situation. If one spouse is offered a new job in another location, the other spouse may be required to leave their current job, which may result in unemployment. It can be difficult for couples because it frequently entails uprooting their lives and starting over in a new location.

Furthermore, if the spouse is not offered a new job, he or she may need help finding work in the new location, leading to unemployment. At last, one spouse may be required to leave work to care for children, aging parents, or other family members. Balancing caregiving responsibilities with work can be difficult, and in some cases, one spouse may need to leave work to provide full-time care.

DISTRIBUTION OF THE UNEMPLOYED BY DEPENDENTS

Table 5 Distribution of the Unemployed by Dependents

Dependents	Count	Percent
0-1	103	33.8%
2-4	137	44.9%
5-6	51	16.7%
7-8	12	3.9%
9 and above	2	0.7%
Total	305	100%

Table 5 summarizes the number of dependents profile of the unemployed and shows that most respondents—137 responses, or 44.9% of the total have 2- 4 dependents. 103 individuals, or 33.8% of the sample, report having 0–1 dependent. 51 out of the total respondents, or 16.7%, said they have 5 or more dependents. Only 12 respondents (3.9% of the entire report) had 7-8 dependents, and only 2 respondents (0.7% of the whole report) had 9 or more. According to these statistics, most unemployed respondents have 2-4 dependents, followed by those who have 0-1 or 5-6 dependents, and a lesser percentage has 7-8 or 9 or more dependents. The objective facts of people's lives have the most significant impact on their level of happiness, and their life satisfaction does not affect the number of dependents (Zhao et al., 2016). It must consider household time resources and requirements variances and the number of adults and children living there (Michalos et al. Ed. 2014).

According to Fingerman et al. (2012), it depends on the situation and the awareness of fulfilling the duties, meeting the obligations, and being responsible for their dependents. Families may become increasingly more important to people's wellness as they age, their need for care increases, and other social relationships, such as those at work, become less significant in their lives. Any person who has assumed full or intermittent responsibility for care or custody of an elder or dependent adult. Moreover, the number of dependents a person has is related to their employment status, with studies indicating that people with more dependents have higher unemployment rates. As a result, policymakers and employers must consider the unique challenges that people with dependents face when developing policies and systems to support work-life balance and provide resources to help people manage their family responsibilities while maintaining stable employment (Thomas, Patricia A, et al. 2017).

B. ASSESSED LEVEL OF LIFE SATISFACTION OF THE RESPONDENTS

The corresponding graph and the Ed Diener Satisfaction with Life scale clearly show that the person expressing their contentment with life falls within the "Extremely Satisfied" bracket. "In most ways, my life is close to my ideal." For this question, the respondent evaluates their degree of satisfaction as "Slightly Satisfied" (5).

Table 6 Level of life satisfaction of the unemployed

SATISFACTION WITH LIFE	Mode	VI
In most ways my life is close to my ideal.	5	Slightly Satisfied
The conditions of my life are excellent.	7	Extremely Satisfied
I am satisfied with my life.	7	Extremely Satisfied
So far, I have gotten the important things I want in life.	7	Extremely Satisfied
If I could live my life over, I would change almost nothing.	7	Extremely Satisfied

Legend: (ES) Extremely Satisfied (S) Satisfied (SS) Slightly Satisfied , (N) Neutral (SD) Slightly Satisfied (D) Dissatisfied (ED) Extremely Dissatisfied

Even while they realize that their life is relatively near to what they would like it to be, there may still be some things they believe could be done better or do not quite fit their ideal existence. "The conditions of my life are excellent." Here, the person ranks their level of satisfaction as "Extremely Satisfied" (score of 7), demonstrating a high level of fulfillment and happiness with their current circumstances. They consider their overall situation good, indicating they are happy with their living arrangements, environment, or other outside elements affecting their well-being. "I am satisfied with my life". The respondent gives this question an "Extremely Satisfied" rating (7), demonstrating a strong sense of fulfillment and general pleasure in their life. They demonstrate a high degree of contentment and imply that they are generally comfortable and contented with their present circumstances." So far, I have gotten the important things I want in life." For this question, the respondent gives themselves an "Extremely Satisfied" rating (scoring 7).

It suggests they feel they have achieved the vital life goals they set out to achieve, demonstrating a sense of satisfaction and contentment in their efforts." If I could live my life over, I would change almost nothing." In this case, the person ranks their degree of satisfaction as "Extremely Satisfied" (7). It suggests that, if given the chance to start over, they would want to make very few, if any, regrets, or significant adjustments to their lives. They appear to have a high level of overall life satisfaction since they exhibit a strong sense of happiness with their prior experiences and choices.

Table 7 Level of Life Satisfaction

Level of Life Satisfaction	Count	Percentage
Extremely Dissatisfied	20	6.6%
Dissatisfied	31	10.2%
Neutral	5	1.6%
Slightly Satisfied	108	35.4%
Satisfied	77	25.2%
Extremely Satisfied	64	21.0%
Total	305	100%

Table 7 illustrates the degree of assessed life satisfaction among respondents of 305 people. Most respondents indicated that they were either slightly (35.4%) or highly (25.2%) content with their lives. Only a lower percentage of people (21.0%) said they were delighted. However, a small portion of the sample claimed to be dissatisfied (10.2%) or highly dissatisfied (6.6%) with their life. Only a tiny proportion of people (1.6%) claimed to feel neutral about their level of life satisfaction. Overall, the results indicate that most of the sample's participants reported feeling at least somewhat satisfied with their lives, while a smaller percentage voiced discontent.

C. LEVEL OF WELL-BEING OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 8 Assessed Level of well-being of the unemployed

PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING		Mode	VI
1	"I like most parts of my personality."	1	Strongly Disagree
2	"When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out so far."	1	Strongly Disagree
3	"Some people wander aimlessly through life, but I am not one of them."	7	Strongly Agree
4	"The demands of everyday life often get me down."	1	Strongly Disagree
5	"In many ways I feel disappointed about my achievements in life."	7	Strongly Agree
6	"Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me."	7	Strongly Agree
7	"I live life one day at a time and don't really think about the future."	7	Strongly Agree
8	"In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live."	1	Strongly Disagree
9	"I am good at managing the responsibilities of daily life."	1	Strongly Disagree
10	"I sometimes feel as if I've done all there is to do in life."	1	Strongly Disagree
11	"For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth."	1	Strongly Disagree
12	"I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how I think about myself and the world."	1	Strongly Disagree
13	"People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others."	1	Strongly Disagree
14	"I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago"	7	Strongly Agree
15	"I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions"	7	Strongly Agree
16	"I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others."	7	Strongly Agree
17	"I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are different from the way most other people think."	1	Strongly Disagree
18	"I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important."	1	Strongly Disagree

Table 8 presents the assessed level of well-being of the respondents. "I like most parts of my personality." - The respondent strongly disagrees with this statement, indicating a lack of self-acceptance or satisfaction with their personality. "When I look at the story of my life, I am pleased with how things have turned out so far." - The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting they feel dissatisfied or unhappy with the current state and trajectory of their life. "Some people wander through life, but I am not one of them." - The respondent strongly agrees, indicating a sense of purpose and direction in their life, distinguishing themselves from those who feel lost or without direction. "The demands of everyday life often get me down." - The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting that they do not find the everyday demands of life burdensome or discouraging.

"In many ways, I feel disappointed about my achievements in life. The respondent strongly agrees, indicating a significant level of disappointment regarding their accomplishments or lack thereof. "Maintaining close relationships has been difficult and frustrating for me." - The respondent strongly agrees, suggesting that they have experienced challenges and frustrations in maintaining close relationships with others.

"I live life one day at a time and do not really think about the future." - The respondent strongly agrees, indicating a present-focused orientation and a lack of emphasis on long-term planning or consideration of the future. "In general, I feel I am in charge of the situation in which I live." - The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting a perception of lack of control or agency in their life circumstances. "I am good at managing the responsibilities of daily life." - The respondent strongly disagrees, implying a belief or feeling that they struggle with managing their daily responsibilities. "I sometimes feel as if I have done all there is to do in life." - The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting they do not feel a sense of fulfillment or completion in their life experiences. "For me, life has been a continuous process of learning, changing, and growth." - The respondent strongly disagrees, indicating a belief that their life has not been characterized by ongoing personal development or positive change. "I think it is important to have new experiences that challenge how I think about myself and the world." -- The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting a resistance or lack of interest in seeking new experiences that can challenge their perspectives. "People would describe me as a giving person, willing to share my time with others." - The respondent strongly disagrees, implying that others would not describe them as generous or willing to invest their time in others. "I gave up trying to make big improvements or changes in my life a long time ago." - The respondent strongly agrees, indicating a sense of resignation or giving up on making significant positive changes or improvements in their life. "I tend to be influenced by people with strong opinions."

The respondent strongly agrees, suggesting susceptibility to being swayed or influenced by individuals who hold strong opinions. "I have not experienced many warm and trusting relationships with others." - The respondent strongly agrees, indicating a lack of substantial, trusting, and warm relationships in their life. "I have confidence in my own opinions, even if they are different from the way most other people think." - The respondent strongly disagrees, suggesting a lack of confidence in holding and expressing opinions that deviate from the majority. "I judge myself by what I think is important, not by the values of what others think is important." - The respondent strongly disagrees, implying that they tend to evaluate themselves based on the values and opinions of others rather than their priorities and beliefs.

According to the responses, it appears that the person has poor psychological health and is generally unhappy with several parts of their life. they describe having trouble establishing close relationships, feeling unsatisfied with their accomplishment, and having trouble accepting themselves. They adopt a mindset of the present because they feel out of control in their current circumstance and find it challenging to handle their everyday tasks. They need more interest in developing personally, trying new things, and significantly bettering their lot in life. They frequently lack warm and trustworthy relationships, are easily swayed by others' strong opinions, and have little faith in their judgment. They also frequently evaluate themselves according to the beliefs and ideals of others rather than their own. Their comments collectively imply a pessimistic view and a need for assistance in enhancing their psychological wellbeing.

Table 9 Assessed Level of Wellbeing

Assessed Level of		
Wellbeing	Count	Percentage
Low	84	27.54%
Moderate	181	59.34%
Above average	22	7.21%
High	18	5.90%
Total	305	100%

Table 9 presents a total of 305 people who were surveyed to gauge their assessed level of well-being based on the data offered. According to the findings, 181 respondents, or 59.34%, indicated that their degree of well-being was moderate. A low level of well-being was reported by 27.54% of the population (84 people). Only 5.90% of respondents (or 18 people) reported a high level of wellbeing, compared to 7.21% (22 people) who reported an above-average level of well-being. With only a tiny percentage claiming above average or high levels of well-being, these data imply that the majority of those polled indicated moderate to low levels of well-being.

D. Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when grouped according to their demographic profile

Table 10 Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when group according to sex

Sex	Z	P-Value	Decision	Remarks
	-		Failed to	Not
Male	0.005	0.996	Reject Ho ₂	Significant
Female				

Table 10 shows the outcomes of a Mann-Whitney U test that was conducted to assess the degree of life satisfaction between men and women. If the nonparametric test is suitable if the data are not regularly distributed. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.996, along with the test statistic (U), which is given as 11614. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.996, which is more than the significance level of 0.05. It shows that there is not enough data to draw any statistically meaningful conclusions about the level of life satisfaction between men and women. Therefore, when comparing the degrees of life happiness between males and females, the MannWhitney U test shows that there is no significant difference in the degree of life satisfaction based on sex.

Research has found gender-related disparities, such as a mean gender difference in subjective well-being and contentment with life. Model confirmation research suggests children are more likely to prefer mates who are the same gender as themselves if they feel more like members of their gender group. Additionally, research has shown that females are happier at school than boys, but there is a dearth of substantial and definitive information on this subject (AlAttayah et.al 2013).

Table 11 Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when group according to Age

Age	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
18-28				
29-39				
40-50	2.299	0.681	Failed to	Not Significant
51-59			Reject Ho ₂	
60 and above				

Table 11 shows the outcomes of a Kruskal-Wallis test that was performed to examine the degree of life satisfaction between various age groups. For data that is not regularly distributed, the Kruskal-Wallis test is applicable. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.681, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 2.299. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.681, which is more than the usual significance level of 0.05. It means that there is not enough data to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the degree of life satisfaction between the various age groups. Therefore, according to the Kruskal-Wallis result, there is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction across the age groups under consideration.

Low life satisfaction has been associated with unemployment in adolescents. Adults' unemployment and mental health have been observed to be connected. Health, while being unemployed, can impact a person's mental health and level of life happiness, though to varying degrees. Some age groups have positive effects, and high life satisfaction improves their social and intellectual functioning, higher academic results, and resistance against complex life events even if they are unemployed (Johansson, 2019).

Table 12 Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when group according to Marital Status

Marital Status	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Single Married Separated Divorced Widowed	8.203	0.084	Failed to Reject Ho ₂	Not Significant

Table 12 shows the outcomes of a Kruskal-Wallis test that was used to examine the degree of life satisfaction across various categories of marital status for data that needs to be regularly distributed. The Kruskal-Wallis test is appropriate. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.084, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 8.203. The verdict is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.084, which is more than the accepted significance level of 0.05. It implies that there is not enough data to draw a statistically meaningful conclusion about the level of life satisfaction among the various marital status categories. Therefore, according to the Kruskal- Wallis result, there is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction across the marital status categories considered in the analysis.

As stated by Van der Meer, P. H. (2014), the impact of unemployment does not significantly differ between married men and women. The impact of having a profession or unemployment is independent of a man's partner's actions on the labor market for males. Compared to married unemployed women, unemployed men exhibit significantly lower levels of well-being. For singles, the researcher observed the same result. Comparatively speaking, single unemployed males are less happy than single unemployed women. People's subjective well-being rises when they have a relationship.

Additionally, we observe that single men are most negatively impacted by unemployment. Having a spouse in men's lives mediates the impact of unemployment. All other effects are small or insignificant (Meer, 2014).

Table 13 Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when group according to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Elementary High School Vocational 2 years college 4 years college	15.657	0.004	Reject Ho ₂	Not Significant

Based on the findings in Table 13 of the Kruskal-Wallis test (H = 15.657, p = 0.004), the information supplied reveals that there is a significant difference in the quality of life satisfaction among different degrees of schooling. It suggests that the amount of life satisfaction differs across the educational attainment groups, rejecting the null hypothesis (Ho). Post hoc tests need to be performed in order to look into the differences further. There is a substantial between elementary school and four-year college groups. A variation in the level of life satisfaction was found in this instance, according to a post hoc analysis (p = 0.003). The other categories of educational attainment, however, did not show any statistically significant differences. In summary, the results show that the groups of educational attainment had significantly different levels of life satisfaction. Notably, between the elementary school and four-year college groups, there are significant variances in life satisfaction.

According to the study, persons with only a primary education were 1.5 times more likely to experience the adverse effects of unemployment on life satisfaction than those with a tertiary education. In general, it clarifies the link between life happiness and unemployment among those with lower levels of education. The results show that unemployment has a significant detrimental effect on these people's well-being and that measures designed to lessen unemployment and increase access to education and training may help them feel more satisfied with their lives (Zon, Reijevneveld, De Leon, Bultmann, 2017).

Table 14 Difference among the assessed level of life satisfaction when group according to Number of Dependents

Number of Dependents	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
0-1 2-4			Failed to Reject Ho ₂	Not Significant
5-6 7-8 9 and above	4.301	0.367		

Table 14 shows the findings of a statistical investigation into the association between the quantity of dependents and the degree of life satisfaction. to ascertain if there is a statistically significant difference in life satisfaction between diverse groups of dependents, the analysis used the Kruskal-Wallis test. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.367 along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 4.301. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.367, which is more than the usual significance level of 0.05. This suggests that there is inadequate data to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the degree of life satisfaction among the various dependent groups.

However, the 'pure' rank-income hypothesis implies that if rank order didn't change, redistribution of higher earnings to lessen inequality most impoverished households. On the other hand, in comparison to other countries, the egalitarian Nordic economies with high tax rates on top incomes often score highest in terms of happiness or life satisfaction, and they also have significantly lower rates of child poverty (Dorling & Koljonen, 2020).

E. DIFFERENCE IN LEVEL OF WELL-BEING WHEN GROUPED ACCORDING TO THEIR DEMO GRAPHIC PROFILE

Table 15 Difference among the assessed level of well-being when group according to Sex

Sex	U value	P-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Male	10867.5	0.266	Failed to Reject Ho ₁	Not Significant
Female				

According to Table 15, a Mann-Whitney U test was likely performed to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between males' and females' levels of life satisfaction. When data are not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney U test is acceptable for comparing independent groups. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.266, along with the test statistic (U), which is given as 10867.5. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.266, which is more than the usual significance level of 0.05. It shows that there is not enough data to draw any statistically meaningful conclusions about the well-being between men and women. Therefore, according to the Mann-Whitney U test, there is no significant difference in the level of well-being based on sex.

As stated by Van der Meer, P. H. (2014), the different levels of well-being are among the various categories. These variations are statistically tested in the tables. Between men and women, there is no difference in well-being.

Table 16 Difference among the assessed level of well-being when group according to Age

Age	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
18-28				
29-39				
40-50	3.29	0.511	Failed to Reject Ho ₁	Significant
51-59				
60 and above				

According to Table 16, a Kruskal-Wallis test was carried out to see if there is a substantial difference between the levels of life satisfaction among various age groups. In situations where the data are not normally distributed, the KruskalWallis test is applicable. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.511, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 3.290.

The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.511, which is more than the usual significance criterion of 0.05. It shows that there is inadequate data to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the degree of well-being between the various age groups. Therefore, according to the Kruskal-Wallis test, there is no significant difference in well-being based on age.

Older adults are more positively associated with psychological well-being than their younger counterparts. Ryff's model states that purpose in life is a critical component of psychological wellness, and older people are more likely to engage in activities that give them a sense of purpose and meaning. The Ryff is a straightforward and relatively short survey that assesses the psychological component of well-being. It is a dynamic concept that includes subjective, social, and psychological dimensions as well as health-related behaviors. Carstensen et al. suggest that perceived limitations in terms of how much longer they have to live lead to a shift in mindset that causes older adults to focus more on activities that are meaningful to them (Abdullahi et al., 2019).

Table 17 Difference among the assessed level of well-being when group according to Marital Status

Marital Status	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Single				
Married				
Separated	0.917	0.922	Failed to Reject Ho ₁	Not Significant
Divorced				
Widowed				

Based on Table 17, a Kruskal-Wallis test to determine if there is a substantial variation in the level of life satisfaction between different marital status groups was conducted. When examining data that is not regularly distributed, the Kruskal-Wallis test is valid. The corresponding p-value is given as 0.922, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 0.917. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.922, which is more than the usual significance level of 0.05. This shows that there is not enough data to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the degree of well-being among the various marital status groups. The Kruskal-Wallis test reveals that the level of well-being is not significantly affected by marital status.

The associations between marital status and well-being are more consistent than age variation. Being single and getting divorced were discovered to be risk factors for depressive symptoms and poorer self-esteem during the 30-year study period, particularly in men. In terms of mental health, dating and cohabitation were no different from marriage, depending on age and gender, especially for women. Dating and cohabitation had erratic correlations. These results imply that the presence of a spouse may be more significant for mental health than marriage itself. Since depression is a deviation from the norm (i.e., a sickness), the results for depressed symptoms were more pronounced and distinct (Grundström et al., 2021).

Table 18 Difference among the assessed level of well-being when group according to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
Elementary High School				
Vocational	1.42	0.841	Failed to Reject Ho ₁	to Not Significant
2-year college				
4-year college				

Referring to Table 18, a Kruskal-Wallis test was carried out to determine whether there is a significant difference in the degree of happiness between various educational attainment groups. When examining data that is not regularly distributed, the Kruskal-Wallis test is valid. The related p-value is given as 0.841, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 1.420. The decision is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis) based on the p-value of 0.841, which is higher than the usual significance level of 0.05. It shows that there is not enough data to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the degree of well-being between the various educational attainment categories. The KruskalWallis test thus concludes that the level of well-being is similar depending on educational attainment.

Based on their study, data from national educational attainment examinations in the UK were gathered to examine whether poorly comprehending students who were first recruited at age 9 still had low academic achievements at the end of primary school (age 11) and at the conclusion of compulsory schooling (age 16). Evidence of low educational achievement among poorly comprehended at age 16 is evident. On virtually all measures, poor comprehends underperformed controls, although there were no significant differences on any of the accomplishment indices when bad comprehends and controls were compared. In contrast to the national average of one in six, over one in two of our poor comprehensions did not get five GCSEs at the A* to C level. Our research shows that weak comprehension is at risk of academic failure at the conclusion of primary school and may also be at a disadvantage at the end of compulsory education when results from age 11 are combined (Ricketts,et. al, 2014).

Table 19 Difference among the assessed level of well-being when group according to Number of Dependents

Number of Dependents	H value	P-value	Decision	Remarks
0-1				
2-4				
5-6	4.789	0.31	Failed to Reject Ho ₁	Not Significant
7-8				
9 and above				

When the data does not follow a normal distribution, the Kruskal-Wallis test is a non-parametric test used to compare three or more independent groups. The associated p-value is given as 0.310, along with the test statistic (H), which is given as 4.789. The result is "Failed to Reject Ho" (null hypothesis), with a pvalue of 0.310 above the accepted significance restriction of 0.05. It shows that there is inadequate information to draw a statistically significant conclusion about a difference in the groups' levels of well-being depending on the presence of dependents. Therefore, according to the Kruskal-Wallis test, based on the number of dependents in the investigated sample, there is no discernible variation in the level of well-being.

Based on McClelland (2023), Not only can losing a job affect family finances. Child development and family stability are impacted by job loss. Unemployment is high among parents themselves. Therefore, parents of dependent children bear a third of the burden of unemployment. The future development and employment prospects of youngsters could be harmed by unemployment. It also looks at how unemployment affects several families. Families who are unemployed experience poverty and hardship, strained relationships, worsened health (although the causal links between these effects are not always obvious), and housing stress.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

In the twenty-first century, unemployment had a significant and far-reaching impact on happiness and life satisfaction. Unemployment can cause financial hardship because people find it difficult to satisfy their fundamental demands and maintain their level of living in today's quickly evolving work environment. Increased tension, anxiety, and a diminished sense of well-being may follow from this. Additionally, the lack of job security and the popularity of contract employment and gig labor can amplify emotions of uncertainty and instability, having a detrimental effect on life satisfaction and mental health. Increased social isolation, a lack of work-life balance, and a blurring of lines between work and home life are just a few of the difficulties that the development of remote work during the COVID-19 epidemic has brought about.

These issues can have an adverse effect on general well-being and life satisfaction. In some nations, the lack of accessible social safety nets and inexpensive healthcare can exacerbate the effects of unemployment, causing more stress and monetary insecurity. Additionally, the pressure to maintain skills and stay up with the quickly evolving job market can cause anxiety and a sense of inadequacy, which can further affect happiness and quality of life. The pervasive impact of social media and the societal expectation of success and achievement can also cause a sense of failure and decreased life satisfaction among unemployed people. Further affecting general well-being and life satisfaction is the effect of unemployment on social relationships, including strained family dynamics and diminished social support.

Finally, the stress and uncertainty experienced by those who are unemployed or working in industries at risk of disruption may increase because of growing knowledge of environmental concerns like climate change and the need for sustainable employment possibilities. The complexity and influence of various socioeconomic, technological, and environmental factors on the impact of unemployment on well-being and life satisfaction in the twenty-first century highlight the need for comprehensive approaches to address the difficulties faced by those who are unemployed.

A. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study are summarized as follows:

1. Profile Background of the respondents

The demographic information in this study includes a sample of 305 people's sex, age, educational level, marital status, and number of dependents. 51.5% of the population was female and 48.5% was male. The majority of responses were in the 18 to 50 age range, with the most significant proportion being between the ages of 40 and 50. The majority of respondents had graduated from high school, with only 20.3% having only received their primary education. Married respondents made up 47.2% of the total, followed by single respondents (37.4%), with negligible numbers of those who were separated, divorced, or widowed. A small minority of respondents had nine or more dependents, whereas the bulk of respondents had 2-4 dependents.

2. Level of Life Satisfaction of the respondents

The majority of the 305 respondents indicated they were moderately (35.4%) or highly (25.2%) satisfied with their lives. While a small minority of respondents stated discontent (10.2%) or extreme unhappiness (6.6%), a lower percentage (21.0%) indicated extreme satisfaction. Overall, it appears from the findings that the majority of respondents were at least somewhat comfortable with their lives, with a smaller proportion expressing displeasure.

3. Level Well-being of the respondents

In a poll of 305 persons, 181 respondents, or 59.34%, they reported having a moderate level of well-being. Only 5.90% (18 people) reported a high level of well-being, and 7.21% (22 people) reported an above-average level, while 27.54% (84 people) reported a low level of well-being. Most respondents reported moderate to low levels of well-being overall, with a small minority reporting above average or high levels.

4. Difference level of life satisfaction according to the Demographic Profile of the respondents

The results presented in the tables suggest that there is no significant difference in Life Satisfaction scores between males and females ($u = 11614$, $p = 0.996 > 0.05$) between different age groups ($h = 2.299$, $p = 0.681 > 0.05$) and across marital status ($h = 8.203$, $p = 0.084 > 0.05$) categories. However, there is a significant difference in life satisfaction based on educational attainment ($h = 15.657$, $p = 0.004 < 0.05$) between individuals with higher levels of educational attainment (Hdf, alpha level = 15.657, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$) with individuals with higher levels of educational attainment tending to have higher levels of life satisfaction. On the other hand, the number of dependents (Hdf, alpha level = 4.301, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$) does not seem to have a significant effect on life satisfaction.

5. Difference in level of well-being when grouped according to their demographic profile

The results indicated that there were no significant differences in well-being scores between males and females ($u = 10867.5$, $p = 0.266 > 0.05$), among the different age groups (Hdf, alpha level = 3.290, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$) across marital status groups (Hdf, alpha level = 0.917, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$), based on educational attainment (Hdf, alpha level = 1.420, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$) and among the various groups based on the number of dependents (Hdf, alpha level = 4.789, $P < \text{or} > 0.05$).

B. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The study's demographic information reveals that the sample population consists of a relatively even distribution of males and females. The majority of respondents fall within the 18 to 50 age range, with the most significant proportion being between the ages of 40 and 50. The study shows that the majority of respondents have completed high school education. Married respondents make up almost half of the total sample population, followed by single respondents. Finally, the study indicates that the bulk of respondents have 2-4 dependents, while only a tiny minority have nine or more dependents.
2. The majority of the respondents indicated that they were slightly satisfied with their life.
3. The majority of the respondents indicated that their level of well-being was moderate.
4. There is no significant difference in the level of life satisfaction in terms of sex, age, marital status, and number of dependents. On the other hand, educational attainment indicates significant differences to consider when analyzing life satisfaction levels in the examined population.
5. There is no significant difference in level of well-being in terms of sex, age, educational background, marital status, and number of dependents.

C. RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and the conclusions generated from the study, the proponent of the study recommended that:

1. **To the unemployed**, it is critical to keep a positive attitude and a proactive mindset to get through unemployment. Keep in mind that this stage is transitory and that finding a new work will be significantly aided by tenacity and positivity. Start by updating and customizing resume to emphasize pertinent experiences and skills. Make sure it stands out and draws potential employers' attention. Attend industry conferences, join online forums, and make connections with people in the target industry to broaden professional network.
2. **The government** has a number of proactive options for tackling the unemployment problem. It should first develop policies and programs for job creation that are intended to boost economic expansion and encourage the creation of new employment possibilities. The government may encourage investment and business growth, which will result in job growth, by forming partnerships with the private sector. Additionally, funding infrastructure improvements can promote long-term economic growth in addition to employment creation. Furthermore, as these companies are important employers, the government should give small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) priority support through funding programs and simplified rules. Furthermore, promoting entrepreneurship and providing resources for startups can foster innovation and generate new

employment prospects. It is also essential for the government to focus on reskilling and upskilling initiatives to meet the demands.

3. Encourage **students** to finish college to help them avoid unemployment. Studies show that those with college degrees are less likely to be jobless than people without degrees. It is because those who have completed college have the information and abilities necessary to succeed in the work market of today, making them more appealing prospects for employers. Encouragement to complete college can aid students in avoiding the adverse effects of unemployment, such as financial instability and lower levels. Obtaining a college degree can result in improved levels of life satisfaction in addition to preventing unemployment. A college degree can help people develop personally by giving them a more comprehensive perspective of the world. Additionally, people with college degrees typically earn more money, which can result in a higher standard of living. Additionally, a college education may present chances for intellectual and social engagement, both of which may enhance.

4. **To future researchers:** We strongly advise future researchers to look into how employment affects happiness and life satisfaction. In order to comprehend the complex relationship between job and personal happiness, this field of study is crucial. They can shed light on the elements that contribute to job satisfaction and general life satisfaction by looking at how employment affects well-being. Policymakers, companies, and people all benefit from understanding the effects of numerous employment factors, such as job security, work-life balance, and professional growth chances. Additionally, investigating potential differences in well-being outcomes across various occupational groups and demographics can help pinpoint areas that require development and intervention. The creation of measures to improve job quality, encourage employee engagement, and promote healthier work environments can be influenced by knowledge of the relationship between employment and well-being. Additionally, researching how long-term employment impacts mental, physical, and total life satisfaction can help establish evidence-based policies and practices that put employee well-being first.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. (2018, July 2). Ryff Scales of Psychological Well-Being | Wabash National Study. Center of Inquiry at Wabash College. <https://centerofinquiry.org/uncategorized/ryff-scales-of-psychological-wellbeing/>
- [2] Axelrad, H., Malul, M., & Luski, I. (2018). Unemployment among younger and older individuals: does conventional data about unemployment tell us the whole story? *Journal for Labour Market Research*, 52(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12651-018-0237-9>
- [3] Bartram, D. (2020). Age and Life Satisfaction: Getting Control Variables under Control. *Sociology*, 55(2), 0038038-52092687. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0038038520926871>
- [4] Berth H., Brahler E., Richter E., Richter Y., Zenger M., (2020). The long-lasting impact of unemployment on life satisfaction: results of a longitudinal study over 20 years in East Germany., *The long-lasting impact of unemployment on life satisfaction: results of a longitudinal study over 20 years in East Germany* - PubMed (nih.gov)
- [5] Boccaro J., Handerson K., Hodge Camilla., & Zabriskie R., (2015) Family Leisure An Integrative Review of Research from Select Journals (PDF) Family Leisure An Integrative Review of Research from Select Journals (researchgate.net).
- [6] Boreham, P., Povey, J., & Tomaszewski, W. (2016). Work and social well-being: the impact of employment conditions on quality of life. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(6), 593– 611. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2015.1027250>
- [7] Brand, J. E. (2015). The Far-Reaching Impact of Job Loss and Unemployment. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 41(1), 359–375. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-071913-043237>
- [8] Brenes-Camacho, G. (2018). Number of children in a household and child wellbeing. *Revista Latinoamericana de Población*, 12(22), 5–31. <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/3238/323856298002/html/>
- [9] Brügger, E., Högrevé, J., Holmlund, M., Kabadayi, S., & Löfgren, M. (2017). Financial well-being: A conceptualization and research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 79, 228– 237. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.03.013>
- [10] Burgard, Sarah A., and Katherine Y. Lin. “Bad Jobs, Bad Health? How Work and Working Conditions Contribute to Health Disparities.” *American Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 57, no. 8, 8 May 2013, pp. 1105–1127, www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3813007/#R89, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764213487347>.

- [11] Butiong, E. J., Gocalin, N., Garcia-Vigonte, F., & Abante, M. V. (2023) A Study on the Inflation and Unemployment of the Philippines through the years Years.Papers.ssrn.com.<https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstractid=4368961>
- [12] Celestine, N., PhD. (2023, March 9). The Ryff Scales of Psychological Wellbeing: Your HowTo Guide. PositivePsychology.com. <https://positivepsychology.com/ryff-scalepsychological-wellbeing/>
- [13] Ciftcioglu C. & Murad B., (2017). The Relationship between Financial Develop Development and Unemployment in Selected Countries of The European Union. The Relationship between Financial Development andUnemployment in Selected Countries of the European Union | EuropeanReview | Cambridge Core
- [14] Clench-Aas, J., & Holte, A. (2018). Measures that increase social equality are effective in improving life satisfaction in times of economic crisis. BMC Public Health, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-6076-3>
- [15] Chen W., Hou F., (2019)., The Effect of Unemployment on Life Satisfaction: A Cross-National Comparison Between Canada, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States. [PDF] The Effect of Unemployment on Life Satisfaction: A Cross-National Comparison Between Canada, Germany, the United Kingdom and the United States | Semantic Scholar
- [16] Clench-Aas, J., & Holte, A. (2018). Measures that increase social equality are effective in improving life satisfaction in times of economic crisis. BMC Public Health, 18(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-6076-3>
- [17] Crammer, C., Kaw, C., Gansler, T., & Stein, K. (2011). Cancer Survivors' Spiritual Well-Being and Use of Complementary Methods: A Report from the American Cancer Society's Studies of Cancer Survivors. Journal of Religion& Health, 50(1), 92–107. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-010-9327-x>
- [18] Denmark Unemployment Rate: Gross: 50 to 59 Years | Economic Indicators | CEIC. (n.d.). www.ceicdata.com. Retrieved April 23, 2023, from <https://www.ceicdata.com/en/denmark/unemployment-rate/unemploymentrate-gross-50-to-59-year>
- [19] Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. W., & Griffin, S. (1985). The Satisfaction With Life Scale. Journal of Personality Assessment, 49(1), 71– 75. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13
- [20] Eichhorst, Werner, et al. "How to Combine the Entry of Young People in the Labour Market with the Retention of Older Workers?" IZA Journal of European Labor Studies, vol. 3, no. 1, 6 Oct. 2014, <https://doi.org/10.1186/2193-9012-3-19>
- [21] Engels, B., Geyer, J., & Haan, P. (2017). Pension incentives and early retirement. LabourEconomics, 47, 216–231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2017.05.006>
- [22] Farré, L., Fasani, F., & Mueller, H. (2018). Feeling useless: the effect of Unemployment on mental health in the Great Recession. IZA Journal of Labor Economics, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40172-018-0068-5>
- [23] Fidelis A., (2020)., The impact of unemployment and psychological well-being., The impact of unemployment and psychological well-being | SciELO in Perspective: Humanities
- [24] Field, T. (2010). Touch for socioemotional and physical well-being: A review. Developmental Review, 30(4), 367–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dr.2011.01.00>
- [25] Fingerman, K. L., Cheng, Y. P., Wesselmann, E. D., Zarit, S., Furstenberg, F., & Birditt, K. S. (2012). Helicopter parents and landing pad kids: Intense parental support of grown children. Journal of Marriage and Family, 74(4), 880–896.
- [26] Francess M-R., & Maitoza R (2014). Unemployment and Families. Job Loss, Unemployment, and Families | The Oxford Handbook of Job Loss and Job Search | Oxford Academic (oup.com)
- [27] Gedikli, C., Miraglia, M., Connolly, S., Bryan, M., & Watson, D. (2022). The relationship between unemployment and wellbeing: an updated metaanalysis of longitudinal evidence. European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359432x.2022>.

- [28] González-Carrasco, M., Casas, F., Malo, S., Viñas, F., & Dinisman, T. (2016). Changes with Age in Subjective Well-Being Through the Adolescent Years: Differences by Gender. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 18(1), 63– 88. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-016-9717-1>
- [29] Hawgood J., Kolves K., Mathieu S., Ross V., Treloar A., (2022). The Role of Unemployment, Financial Hardship, and Economic Recession on Suicidal Behaviors and Interventions to Mitigate Their Impact: A Review. *The Role of Unemployment, Financial Hardship, and Economic Recession on Suicidal Behaviors and Interventions to Mitigate Their Impact: A Review - PubMed (nih.gov)*
- [30] Högberg B., Voßemer J., & Strandh M., (2019)., Unemployment, well-being, and the moderating role of education policies: A multilevel study., *Unemployment, well-being, and the moderating role of education policies: A multilevel study - Björn Högberg, Jonas Voßemer, Michael Gebel, Mattias Strandh, 2019 (sagepub.com)*
- [31] Hsu, T.-L., & Barrett, A. E. (2020). The Association between Marital Status and Psychological Well-being: Variation across Negative and Positive Dimensions. *Journal of Family Issues*, 0192513X2091018. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513x20910184>
- [32] Kagan, J. (2022, June 24). What Is Quality of Life? Why It's Important and How to Improve It. *Investopedia*. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/q/quality>
- [33] Milner, A., et al. “Cause and Effect in Studies on Unemployment, Mental Health and Suicide: A Meta-Analytic and Conceptual Review.” *Psychological Medicine*, vol. 44, no. 5, 9 July 2013, pp. 909–917, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291713001184>
- [34] Monsef, A., Abolfazl, S., & Mehrjardi. (2018). Effect of Unemployment on Health Capital. *Econ. Rev*, 22(4), 1016–1033. https://ier.ut.ac.ir/article_67853_4aaccd0120836c397be6c2e6d6b25356.pdf
- [35] Moksnes, U. K., & Espnes, G. A. (2013). Self-esteem and life satisfaction in adolescents—gender and age as potential moderators. *Quality of Life Research*, 22(10), 2921–2928. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-013-0427-4>
- [36] Möwisch, D., Brose, A., & Schmiedek, F. (2020). Do Higher Educated People Feel Better in Everyday Life? Insights From a Day Reconstruction Method Study. *Social Indicators Research*, 153(1), 227–250. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-020-02472-y>
- [37] Mühlböck, M., Steiber, N., & Kittel, B. (2020). Learning to keep the faith?
- [38] Further education and perceived employability among young unemployed. *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 0143831X2094421. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143831x20944211>
- [39] National Center for Education Statistics. (2017). The NCES Fast Facts Tool provides quick answers to many education questions (National Center for Education Statistics). *Ed.gov; National Center for Education*
- [40] Philippine Statistics Authority. (2016). Philippine Statistics Authority | Republic of the Philippines. *Psa.gov.ph*. <https://psa.gov.ph/>
- [41] Pollmann-Schult, M. (2014). Parenthood and Life Satisfaction: Why Don't Children Make People Happy? *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 76(2), 319–336. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jomf.12095>
- [42] Tumin, D., & Qian, Z. (2015). Unemployment and the Transition From Separation to Divorce. *Journal of Family Issues*, 38(10), 1389–1413. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513x15600730>
- [43] UNESCO. (2019, April 4). Education for health and well-being. UNESCO. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-health-and-well-being>
- [44] Vandalen, H. P., & Henkens, K. (2002). Early-retirement reform: can it and will it work? *Ageing and Society*, 22(2), 209–231. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s0144686x02008656>
- [45] Van Zon, S. K. R., Reijneveld, S. A., Mendes de Leon, C. F., & Bültmann, U. (2017). The impact of low education and poor health on unemployment varies by work life stage. *International Journal of Public Health*, 62(9) 997–1006. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-017-0972-7>